

Mediated spectroelectrochemical determination of holo-transferrin reduction potential using a flow cell with disposable screen-printed indium-tin oxide electrode

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Calculation of the holo-transferrin reduction potential

Upon application of potential to the solution containing holo-transferrin ($\text{Fe}_2^{\text{III}}\text{-Tf}$) and methyl viologen (MV^{2+}) as a mediator, the following reactions occur:[1–3]

Equation S1 denotes the reduction of colorless MV^{2+} to the blue colored radical $\text{MV}^{\bullet+}$ ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 604 \text{ nm}$, $\varepsilon_{604}(\text{MV}^{\bullet+}) = 1.69 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)[4] at the electrode. The formed $\text{MV}^{\bullet+}$ in turn reduces $\text{Fe}_2^{\text{III}}\text{-Tf}$ ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 465 \text{ nm}$, $\varepsilon_{465}(\text{Fe}_2^{\text{III}}\text{-Tf}) = 4.8 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)[3] to $\text{Fe}_2^{\text{II}}\text{-Tf}$ in the solution, yielding MV^{2+} (equation S2). Considering that the Tf affinity for Fe^{II} is multiple orders of magnitude lower than that for Fe^{III} , the produced $\text{Fe}_2^{\text{II}}\text{-Tf}$ dissociates to Fe^{2+} and apo-Tf (equation S3, where $K_D = 10^{-5.7} \text{ M}^2$).[5]

In this work, when the potential is swept to increasingly negative values, the decrease in concentration of $\text{Fe}_2^{\text{III}}\text{-Tf}$ from the initial value, $[\text{Fe}_2^{\text{III}}\text{-Tf}]_0$, can be followed at 465 nm (molar absorbances of Fe^{2+} , $\text{Fe}_2^{\text{II}}\text{-Tf}$ and apo-Tf are all approximately zero at this wavelength). However, the reduced mediator, $\text{MV}^{\bullet+}$, has a non-zero absorbance at 465 nm (A_{465}) and a separate identical SEC experiment with MV^{2+} alone is required to provide background correction for the absorbance of $\text{Fe}_2^{\text{III}}\text{-Tf}$. [1,2,6] In order to properly apply the background correction, it is crucial that the initial concentrations of the mediator, $[\text{MV}^{2+}]_0$, are equal in both SEC experiments. The value of $[\text{Fe}_2^{\text{III}}\text{-Tf}]$ for each measurement can then be calculated from the background-corrected value of A_{465} and known values for $\varepsilon_{465}(\text{Fe}_2^{\text{III}}\text{-Tf})$ and optical path length of the cell (determined experimentally from the initial value of A_{465} corresponding to $[\text{Fe}_2^{\text{III}}\text{-Tf}]_0$).

For each measurement, the concentration of $\text{MV}^{\bullet+}$ can be calculated from the values of A_{604} and known values for $\varepsilon_{604}(\text{MV}^{\bullet+})$ and optical path length of the cell. It is known that the reduced mediator radical $\text{MV}^{\bullet+}$ can dimerize in the solution and the corresponding equilibrium must be considered (equation S4, where $K_{\text{MV}} = 10^{-2.9} \text{ M}^{-1}$):[4]

The concentrations of the dimer and the remaining oxidized mediator are then calculated as $[(\text{MV}^{\bullet+})_2] = K_{\text{MV}} [\text{MV}^{\bullet+}]^2$ and $[\text{MV}^{2+}] = [\text{MV}^{2+}]_0 - ([\text{MV}^{\bullet+}] + 2 [(\text{MV}^{\bullet+})_2])$, where $[\text{MV}^{2+}]_0$ is the initial concentration of the mediator. The corresponding cell equilibrium potential in V vs. NHE, E_{cell} , can then be calculated as:[3]

$$E_{\text{cell}} = E^{0'} \left(\text{MV}^{2+} / \text{MV}^{\bullet+} \right) - \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{[\text{MV}^{\bullet+}]}{[\text{MV}^{2+}]}, \quad (\text{S5})$$

where E^0 ($MV^{2+}/MV^{•+}$) = -0.449 V vs. NHE is the known reduction potential of the mediator corresponding to equation S1.[7] It should be noted that the NHE refers to 1 N strong acid, whereas the SHE refers to the hydrogen ion having unit activity and no ionic interactions, corresponding to the difference of approximately 5.7 mV at 25°C.[8] Specifically, the Nernst equation, $n F E = -R T \ln K$, for the reduction defined as $2 H^+$ (1 N, activity ≈ 0.8) + $2 e^- \rightarrow H_2$ (fugacity ≈ 100 kPa) at 25°C yields $E = E^0 - 29.6 \log [1 / (0.8)^2]$ for the potential given in mV, and therefore E (SHE) = E (NHE) + 5.7 mV. This correction was used in the calculation of E_{cell} and E^0 ($Fe_2^{III/II}\text{-Tf}$).

Importantly, depending on the experimental values of $[MV^{2+}]_0$ and $[MV^{•+}]$, failure to account for the dimerization of $MV^{•+}$ (equation S4) leads to the error in the calculation of the cell equilibrium potential, ΔE_{cell} , given as:

$$\Delta E_{\text{cell}} = -\frac{RT}{F} \ln \left(1 - \frac{2K_{\text{MV}} [MV^{•+}]^2}{[MV^{2+}]_0 - [MV^{•+}]} \right). \quad (\text{S6})$$

For each data point (E_{cell} vs. $[Fe_2^{III}\text{-Tf}]$), the values of $[Fe_2^{II}\text{-Tf}]$ are calculated from the following expression taking into account the reaction given by equation S3:[2,9,10]

$$x^{(n+1)} + \frac{K_D}{n^n} x - [R] \frac{K_D}{n^n} = 0, \quad (\text{S7})$$

where $x = [\text{apo-Tf}]$, $n = 2$ for $Fe_2^{III}\text{-Tf}$ and $[R] = [Fe_2^{III}\text{-Tf}]_0 - [Fe_2^{III}\text{-Tf}]$. Solving for x yields $[Fe_2^{II}\text{-Tf}] = [R] - x$.

Finally, provided that the cell is at equilibrium at each point, the formal reduction potential of holo-transferrin, E^0 ($Fe_2^{III/II}\text{-Tf}$), and the apparent number of transferred electrons, n_{app} , can be estimated from the Nernst plot corresponding to the following expression:

$$E_{\text{cell}} = E^0(Fe_2^{III/II}\text{-Tf}) + \frac{RT}{n_{\text{app}} F} \ln \frac{[Fe_2^{III}\text{-Tf}]}{[Fe_2^{II}\text{-Tf}]}. \quad (\text{S8})$$

At 25°C and using base 10 logarithm, the equation S8 reduces to the familiar:

$$E_{\text{cell}} = E^0(Fe_2^{III/II}\text{-Tf}) + \frac{59.2 \text{ mV}}{n_{\text{app}}} \log \frac{[Fe_2^{III}\text{-Tf}]}{[Fe_2^{II}\text{-Tf}]}. \quad (\text{S9})$$

Electrochemistry of the mediator MV^{2+} in the spectroelectrochemical cell

In order to evaluate the ITO screen-printed electrode as an electrochemical interface for the reduction of MV^{2+} and in turn the reduction of Fe_2^{III} -Tf, cyclic voltammetry of a 5 mM solution of MV^{2+} in the deaerated buffer was performed at a scan rate of $\nu = 0.2 \text{ V s}^{-1}$, showing a quasi-reversible single-electron process with $E_{1/2} = -681 \text{ mV vs. Ag/AgCl}$ (Figure S1). The cell reference potential of $E(\text{Ag/AgCl}) = +232 \text{ mV vs. NHE}$ was calculated by comparing to the known value of $E^0(MV^{2+}/MV^{•+}) = -0.449 \text{ V vs. NHE}$. [7]

Figure S1. Electrochemical evaluation of MV^{2+} in the spectroelectrochemical cell: cyclic voltammetry of 5 mM MV^{2+} (0.1 M PIPES, pH 7.4, 0.5 M KCl, $\nu = 0.2 \text{ V s}^{-1}$).

The electrode surface area, $A = 0.114 \pm 0.001 \text{ cm}^2$, was determined chronocoulometrically (Figure S2) in the same solution using a known value of the diffusion coefficient, $D(MV^{2+}) = 0.86 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. [7,11] The values of the initial potential, E_1 , and the step potential, E_2 , were selected to be approximately 250 mV more positive or negative, respectively, than the $E_{1/2}$ of the $MV^{2+}/MV^{•+}$ couple, as determined by cyclic voltammetry.

Figure S2. Electrochemical evaluation of MV^{2+} in the spectroelectrochemical cell: chronocoulometry of 5 mM MV^{2+} (0.1 M PIPES, pH 7.4, 0.5 M KCl), $t_{\max} = 0.4$ s, $E_1 = -0.45$ V, $E_2 = -0.95$ V. Potentials are given vs. Ag/AgCl reference. **Inset:** Anson plot of the observed dependence of Q vs. $t^{1/2}$.

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